

LIME AND POZZOLAN BINDING CONTAINING ADDITIVES/SET ACCELERATORS FOR USE IN MORTARS

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ABSTRACT

Searching for low environmental impact materials for use in mortars, lime-metakaolin binders can be a great alternative. However their long hardening process does not please this binder be used in current constructions. Little is known about its workability and setting time. Therefore, this work studied the rheological behavior and the influence of a setting accelerating agents in pastes containing lime-metakaolin. The initial results showed that metakaolin contributed to lower yield strength in relation to the lime paste, but the setting time was still very long.

KEYWORDS

Setting time; Rheology; Metakaolin; lime.

INTRODUCTION

Lime mortars stand out in construction from ancient times until at least the beginning of the 20th century (VEIGA, 2018). In addition to lime and sand, additions of pozzolanic materials were also applied in old constructions (SOUSA, 2014). The vast majority of historic buildings found proved to be durable and compatible with their structural units, but the restoration of masonry walls is an indispensable event over the years (AGGELAKOPOULOU; BAKOLAS; MOROPOULOU, 2011).

With the emergence of Portland cement, lime mortars and the techniques for preparing and applying them ended up being forgotten (VEIGA, 2018). However, for restoration interventions in historic buildings, it is necessary to ensure physical and chemical compatibility of the new mortars, respecting the old ones (GAMEIRO et al., 2012). Due to this, several works in the literature have sought to investigate the composition of the original mortars of historic buildings in order to try to reproduce another compatible mortar nowadays (MENEZES, 2019; VEIGA, VELOSA and MAGALHÃES, 2009).

Lime mortars, compared to those made of Portland cement, take a long time to harden, in addition to having lower mechanical strength (GAMEIRO et al., 2014). According to this author, studies indicate that the addition of pozzolan to lime reduces this hardening time. However, this reduction is still very small when compared to those Portland cement mortars. According to Veiga (2018), historical mortars have limited and infrequent use nowadays and the slow hardening time is pointed out as one of the limiting factors for their use. The use of pozzolans mixed with lime and some type of setting accelerating agent can contribute to this issue of hardening time, making it possible to obtain a type of cementitious binder suitable for use in the reality of historic buildings, as well as for the conventional constructions .

Among the most used pozzolans, metakaolin stands out. Metakaolin is already widespread and commercialized worldwide, as well as in Brazil. But several other pozzolans are also used, and many

of them come from industrial or urban waste (VIEIRA, 2005; AZEREDO, 2012; CARVALHO, 2016). In Paraíba, there are several ceramic brick factories that generate a lot of waste, which has already been studied in several works, proving to be a good pozzolanic material (VIEIRA, 2005; CARNEIRO, MOURA E LEITO, 2009; CARVALHO, 2016; RIBEIRO et.al., 2017; SINHORELLI, 2019). Also worth mentioning is the waste from kaolin processing in the Junco do Seridó-PB region. Many of these industries throw their waste into nature without an adequate destination (NÓBREGA, 2007; MENEZES, 2009) and several studies have shown the potential of this waste in mortars and concrete, either as a pozzolanic material or as an aggregate (MORAES, 2007). ; NÓBREGA, 2007). ; MENEZES, 2007; ROCHA, 2008; REZENDE, 2008; DAYS 2010; AZEREDO, 2012; OLIVEIRA, 2016; AQUINO et al., 2019). Thus, the focus of this work will be to evaluate the behavior of lime and pozzolan-based pastes and mortars (commercial and from waste), against the action of additives/agents in order to accelerate their hardening. Therefore, one can then make use of an alternative and more sustainable binder for the present day.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In Table 1 we can check the materials used in the research and some pertinent information regarding them.

Table 1: Materials used in the analyses.

materials	Information
Hydrated Lime (CH-II)	Hydrated lime type II, acquired in the construction materials trade in the city of Campina Grande/PB
Portland Cement (CP-V)	CP-V ARI
Calcined Kaolin (CC)	Coming from a factory in Juazeirinho - PB and calcined in the laboratory
Metakaolin (MC)	Purchased in the local market of João Pessoa
plasticizer additive	Set and hardening accelerator additive for concrete and mortar brand Sika-3 Plus
Calcium Chloride (CaCl ₂)	Bought at local trade
Water	Provided by the Water and Sewerage Company of Paraíba in the city of Campina Grande/PB

The studies started with the use of the following materials: hydrated lime type II (CH-II), calcined kaolin (CC), commercial metakaolin (MC), commercial additive of the Sika-3 Plus set accelerator type and calcium chloride (CaCl₂). It is worth mentioning that the first step of the methodology involved the physical, chemical, mineralogical and microstructural characterization of the materials added to the theoretical foundation, while the second step involved the laboratory analysis.

Table 2 presents the results of the physical analyzes performed on the materials used. The determination of the specific mass followed the procedures described in NBR 16605 (ABNT, 2017) and the unit mass was determined in the loose state using a container of known mass and volume, where three readings were taken for each material and the value was considered average of them. The values referring to the additive were provided by the manufacturer. The values referring to the unitary and specific masses were taken, as well as the specific area of the CP-V cement were also taken from Oliveira et. al (2019). Regarding the plasticizer additive, the unit mass value was taken from the product's technical sheet (SIKA, 2020).

Table 2: Physical characteristics of materials.

Material	Unit Mass (g/cm ³)	Specific Mass (g/cm ³)	Specific Area (cm ² /g)
CP-V cement	0.890	2.92	24,800
Additive	1,06 ± 0,02 (fornecido pelo fabricante)	-	-
hydrated lime type II (CH-II)	1.00	2.73	-
Calcined Kaolin (CC)	0.43	2.54	-
Metakaolin (MC)	0.41	2.59	-

To make the mixtures of the samples was used the Mixer Philco 3 in 1 PMX600 600W of 600W of power. It has two speeds and a stainless steel blade.

The dosages of the samples were made from the addition of percentages of CP-V and additive over the total value of the binder. The lime:pozzolan ratio adopted was set at 1:1 and established based on studies previously carried out (AZEREDO, 2012; GAMEIRO, 2014; FORTES-REVILLA et.al., PAPAYANI and STEFANIDOU, 2006; VELOSA et. al, 2009). In Table 3, the details of the mixtures are presented. Initially, a value of 1.0 was adopted for the water/binder (w/b) ratio, as performed by Bakotas et al. (2006) and Azerêdo (2012). For this work, w/b ratios of 0.9 and 0.8 were also adopted, in order to verify the behavior of mortars with lower water contents.

Table 3: Detail of the samples for the characterization tests.

Sample	CH-II (%)	CC (%)	CP-V (%)	H ₂ O (%)	MC (%)	CaCl ₂ (%)	Additive (%)
CCC	50	50	0	90	0	0	0
CCCCI	50	50	1	90	0	0	0
CCCA	50	50	0	90	0	0	0.5
CCCCC5	50	50	0	90	0	5	0
CCCCC10	50	50	0	90	0	10	0
CCC	50	50	0	80	0	0	0
CCCCI	50	50	1	80	0	0	0
CCCA	50	50	0	80	0	0	0.5
CCCCC5	50	50	0	80	0	5	0
CCCCC10	50	50	0	80	0	10	0
LIME	100	0	0	100	0	0	0
CMC	50	0	0	100	50	0	0
CMCCI	50	0	1	100	50	0	0
CMCA	50	0	0	100	50	0	0.5

CMCCC5	50	0	0	100	50	5	0
CMCCC10	50	0	0	100	50	10	0
CCC	50	50	0	100	0	0	0
CCCCI	50	50	1	100	0	0	0
CCCA	50	50	0	100	0	0	0.5
CCCCC5	50	50	0	100	0	5	0
CCCCC10	50	50	0	100	0	10	0

In preparing the samples for premixing, the dry material was placed in the water slowly to avoid loss of material. After that, a time of 30 s was allowed for sedimentation in order to facilitate homogenization. After performing this procedure, the sample was mixed for 90s with the mixer at speed 2. After that, the sample is scraped and mixed with the aid of a spatula for 30s and, finally, the sample is mixed for 90s with the mixer on speed 2. In samples where there is the addition of additive or calcium chloride, both materials are added to the water and then the dry materials are inserted into the container for mixing.

After homogenization of the material, the rheological behavior of the paste was verified, and its characteristics (apparent viscosity, shear rate and shear stress) were measured using the Discovery HR-1 hybrid rheometer serial equipment: v4.5.0.42498.

To obtain and evaluate thixotropy, a test of three time intervals was carried out with the different formulations of calcined kaolin pastes. According to SANTOS (2017) et. al. MEZGER (2011), this test is also called "3ITT" (three time intervals test). For this study, in the first time step of this thixotropy test, the sample is cut under constant low rotation for 1min to obtain the viscosity, which will be used as a reference. In the second time interval, the rotation is suddenly increased to a value 1000 times greater and then kept constant for a period of time, using the time of 50 s in the present study. The thixotropy test contributes to the analysis of the recovery of the structure of the sample after being subjected to a small shear rate in the first interval, a higher rate in a second interval and returning to the initial rate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Observing figures 1, 2 and 3 it is possible to notice the non-linear behavior of the curves, which is characteristic of non-Newtonian fluids. Furthermore, the curves suggest a pseudoplastic behavior of the pastes. The same happened in the work of Azeredo et al. (2017) and Oliveira (2019).

Figure 1: Graphs referring to shear rate versus shear stress of lime and calcined kaolin samples with a water/binder ratio of 0.8.

Figure 2: Graphs referring to shear rate versus shear stress of lime and calcined kaolin samples with a water/binder ratio of 0.9.

Figure 3: Graphs referring to shear rate versus shear stress of lime and calcined kaolin samples with a water/binder ratio of 1.

It is also verified that all curves need an initial shear stress for yielding to occur. Comparing with the data obtained when using the content of 1,0 for the water/binder ratio, it is noticeable that there was, with the other levels used, an increase in the value of this initial shear stress necessary for the flow to occur. It is worth noting that the greater this initial tension required, the greater the difficulty that the fluid has to flow. The pastes that present the highest initial shear stress are: CCCI (addition of CP-V) for the 0.8 content and CCC for the 0.9 content.

From figures 4 and 5, the pseudoplastic behavior of the pastes is evident, as the viscosity decreases as the shear rate increases. The same occurred with the works by Betioli et al. (2009), Teixeira et al. (2014) and Oliveira (2019), about cement pastes.

Figure 4: Graphs referring to shear rate versus viscosity of lime and calcined kaolin samples with a water/binder ratio of 0.8.

Figure 5: Graphs referring to shear rate versus viscosity of lime and calcined kaolin samples with a water/binder ratio of 0.9.

The data displayed in Figure 6 show that all samples with metakaolin and the model sample containing only lime, need an initial shear stress (σ_0) for yielding to occur. Added to this, it can be seen that the mixtures of CAL and CMCCI required a higher initial shear stress. This means that those mentioned had greater difficulty in starting the flow. This result was due to the components of the samples having a unit mass greater than the components of the others. The samples that required a lower initial shear stress were the CMC and CMCCC5 samples. According to Pedrajas et al. (2014) and Kashani et al. (2014), several factors are directly related to yield stress. Among some of these we can mention the grain mineralogy, the inter-particle forces and the particle roughness.

Figure 6: Graphs referring to shear rate versus shear stress of lime and metakaolin samples with a water/binder ratio of 1.

THIXOTROPY TEST

With the decrease in water content, the slurry with lime and kaolin (CCC) has a considerable increase in its initial viscosity, as well as with the slurry with additive (CCCA), as shown in Figure 7. All pastes have a progressive increase in their initial viscosity with the reduction of the water content used, this increase being the most expressive in the lime and kaolin paste. And this higher initial viscosity implies a greater difficulty in the flow of the paste.

Figure 7: Viscosity as a function of time of lime pastes with calcined kaolin.

Furthermore, through Figure 8, it can be seen that the CMC and CMCCI samples had a higher initial viscosity. This means that those mentioned had greater difficulty in starting the flow. This result was due to the components of the samples having a unit mass greater than the components of the others. The samples that required a lower initial viscosity were samples CMCCC5 and CMCCC10.

Figure 8: Viscosity as a function of time of lime pastes with metakaolin.

It is possible to observe that there is a regeneration of the structure after the application of a higher shear rate than the initial rate and that it manages to break the internal structure. All samples are able to recover their initial viscosity when the paste is subjected to low rotation again. This means that they can gain yield strength after being subjected to shear rate.

CONCLUSION

With the results obtained, it was possible to verify that the lime and metakaolin pastes and the calcined lime and kaolin pastes, even with the additives, present flow curves that approach the pseudoplastic behavior. And that, unlike lime and metakaolin pastes, all additives used in calcined kaolin pastes resulted in an increase in viscosity. In addition, it is observed how the decrease in the water content used in the pastes contributes to an increase in its initial viscosity, which leads to greater difficulty in flow and contributes to a faster hardening of the paste. Therefore, it is possible to conclude that the use of additives, calcined kaolin and metakaolin collaborate to improve the results of the pastes, as they present progress and increase in their initial viscosity. And it is evident that waste from kaolin processing can have a useful and beneficial destination for the environment.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.